

COMPRESSION AFTER IMPACT (CAI) BEHAVIOR OF CF/PIXA STIFFENED PANELS FOR HSCT EMPENNAGE

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SUMMARY Compression after impact (CAI) behavior of stiffened panels using T-shaped stringers made of heat resistant thermoplastic composites, CF/PIXA, was obtained by tests at room and elevated temperatures of 180 deg. C. Excellent impact resistance was verified for this composite system particularly for stiffened panels with the special fusion bonding film. Room temperature CAI strengths of CF/PIXA stiffened panels were found to be slightly better than CF/PEEK stiffened panels. Relationships between temperature and CAI strengths for CF/PIXA stiffened panels were compared with the results for flat plates and a compatibility between flat plate strengths and stiffened panel strength was identified. It is clarified that damage tolerance properties of CF/PIXA stiffened structure are so remarkable at room temperature that almost no strength reduction was observed. Its damage tolerance capability is quite excellent also at high temperature for High Speed Civil Transport structure.

KEYWORDS: Experiments, Impact, Heat Resistant Thermoplastic Composites, Fusion Bonding, Ultrasonic C-Scan, Local Buckling, Failure Mode

INTRODUCTION

High Speed Civil Transport (HSCT) in Mach range of 2.0 – 2.4 is expected to be realized in some years later for fulfilling air transportation demand with shorter travel time. Affordable ticket price is a key issue for making such aircraft commercially attractive and it means that a number of passengers should be much more than current aircraft, Concorde, and that such aircraft should be able to fly over Pacific Ocean. In order to achieve these challenging goals, serious weight reduction by employing composite materials is the most important technical problem governing feasibility of this HSCT. Key requirements for such composites are thermal stability under exposure to high temperature air up to 177 deg. C for long time in order of several ten thousand hours and excellent damage tolerance properties to allow sufficiently large design critical values for light weight structures. One

promising candidate composite material is carbon fiber (IM-7)/PIXA system based on a new high-temperature thermoplastic polyamide resin developed by Mitsui Chemicals Co. LTD in Japan¹⁾.

As one of the major critical strength evaluations of this material system in a coupon level, compression strength after impact (CAI) tests were conducted at room and elevated temperatures up to 230 deg. C using SACMA method²⁾ at 6.7J/mm impact. These data were compared with open-hole-compression (OHC) strengths for the same material obtained by the authors in parallel and compared with SACMA-CAI results of carbon fiber/Bis-Male-Imide (5260)³⁾. A good potential of the material of the present concern was exhibited.

As the next and first structural step in strength data acquisition, CAI strength tests are conducted for several stiffened panels of CF/PIXA with T-section stiffeners at room temperature and 180 deg. C. It is not an easy work to conduct structural CAI tests at high temperature and a special loading edge clamping device was invented. By comparing such damage tolerance behavior at room and elevated temperature points, great potential of CF/PIXA as structural material of HSCT is discussed and verified in this paper. These tests were also intended to acquire actual allowable strength or strain for the fatigue test of a model wing box made of CF/PIXA under variable environmental temperature.

DESCRIPTION OF TESTED MATERIAL

Among several heat resistant thermoplastic (H RTP) resins known to us, the family of PIX based on AURUM[®] polyimide resin are developed in Japan by the effort of Mitsui Chemicals Co. Ltd¹⁾. Four types in the chronological order, PIX, PIXA, PI-SP and PIXA-M are developed and available in the market. Several properties of neat resin are listed in Table 1. As stated before, material system selected in NAL H RTP structure project was CF(IM-7)/PIXA in accordance with a balance of material properties.

TABLE 1 RESIN PROPERTIES OF PIX FAMILY

	PIX	PIXA	PI-SP	PIXA-M
Crystallinity(Crs)	Crs.	Semi-Crs.	Non-Crs.	Non-Crs.
Gl. Trns. Tmp.(deg.C)	249	252	254	235
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	2.75	2.84	2.65	-
Tensile Strength(MPa)	92.2	89.2	91.2	83.4

Test items conducted were Open Hole Compression (OHC: {(45/0/-45/90)⁴/sym.}, 38×118.0×4.0^t, and 6.35^D), No Hole Compression (NHC: {(45/0/-45/90)⁴/sym.}, 25.4×105.4×4.0^t), and CAI tests in SACMA²⁾ method at 6.7J/mm impact. They were all conducted at room and elevated temperatures and up to 230 deg. C. Size and stacking sequence of plate CAI are as follows: 101.6×152.4×4.0^t and {(45/0/-45/90)⁴/sym.}, respectively. Results of these compression tests of quasi-isotropic coupons were reported in Ref.4. It should be noted that all dimensions quoted above are only nominal values in mm

unit and that the actual values were measured for all the specimens. Elastic moduli obtained from unidirectional coupons at elevated temperatures will be used for numerical predictions of buckling behavior stated later.

SUMMARY OF CAI AND OHC TEST RESULTS

As a baseline for a comparison of panel CAI tests, summary of SACMA CAI and OHC test results is first given here. In SACMA CAI tests, applied impact energy normalized by thickness was specified to 6.7 J/mm, corresponding to 1500 lbf×in/in, and all impact tests were conducted at ambient temperature. Projected delamination areas were measured by using a modern ultrasonic C-scanner, SDS 3300 system by Krautkramer Japan Co.LTD. The experimental details such as strain and displacement measurements in CAI developed in NAL^{5,6)} were again traced in the present tests. All tests were conducted using a screw-driven Instron 1128 machine. An environmental chamber was attached to the testing machine for elevated temperature tests at 150, 200 and 230 deg. C.

Fig. 1 Temperature Dependency of Flat Plate CAI Strengths and Its Comparison with OHC Behavior

The SACMA CAI results are indicated in Fig. 1 with reference data for CF/bis-male-imide (5260)³⁾ where all legends indicate an average of three data. This figure describes that the present IM7/PIXA system exhibits very similar to slightly higher CAI strengths in short term than CF/BMI as test temperature increases. Previous CAI data⁷⁾ for similar thermoplastic PI composites (CF/PI-SP) are also plotted in Fig. 1 where the test method was NASA and normalized energy level was 4J/mm. If we notice that the energy difference between the current PIXA (6.7 J/ mm) and previous PI-SP (4J/mm), CAI strengths of CF/PIXA system are considered to be excellent. It can be also seen that CAI values of IM7/PIXA are better than CF/5260 particularly over 200 deg. C. Because it is already clarified that a difference in CAI strengths caused by methods (NASA and SACMA) is trivial⁶⁾, the present improvement is supposed to be brought by a better quality of prepreg and refined fabrication process.

Long term strength behavior under exposure to high temperature air and evaluated in OHC

was presented in Ref. 8. The results of thermoplastic poly-imide (CF/PI-SP at that time) were much more excellent than other BMI composites. This sort of strengths including CAI after long time exposure should be the decision making properties for the final selection of HSCT material systems. As reference strengths of CF/PIXA, OHC results obtained by the authors are compared in Fig.1. Data scatter can be found to be trivial. A similarity in data trend between CAI and OHC is found in this figure. To be exact, OHC data are always a little smaller than CAI data in the present case. If we can assume this similarity holds in long time exposure tests, it is very sure that CAI strengths are quite insensitive to high temperature air.

DESCRIPTION OF STIFFENED PANELS FOR CAI TESTS

Outline of stiffened panel specimens made of CF/PIXA is described here. Two kinds of stiffened panels with one T-shaped stringer (1T) and with two T-shaped stringers (2T), similar to the author's previous work⁹⁾ with four T, were fabricated by one supporting company, Fuji Heavy Industries Co. LTD, Japan, using fusion bonding technique with autoclaves. Shape and dimensions of the 1T and 2T panels are shown in Figs.2 and 3, respectively. In order to avoid

Fig.2 1T Panel Shape and Dimensions
(Same Gage Location All Panels)

Fig.3 2T Panel Shape and Dimensions
(Different Gage Location in some Panels)

later duplication of illustrations, strain and dial gage locations are also indicated in these drawings as much as possible. For both kinds, five panels (01-05) were fabricated. A 2T panel has larger dimensions than 1T, although they are not sufficient in size to realize the unaffected local buckling state by peripheral supports. A size of an environmental chamber for the Instron machine used (1128) enforces these rather small sizes of the stiffened panels. The purpose of a 1T panel is to conduct a test under less effects of local inter-bay buckling.

For fusion bonding between skin and stiffeners, a thermoplastic polyimide film, Regulus PIXA-M by Mitsui Chem. Co. was utilized. Stacking sequences were (45/90/-45/0/0/45/90/-45/0)_{sym.}: 18 plies for skin, (45/0/-45/90/45/0/0/-45/0/0/-45/0/0/45/90/-45/0/45)_{sym.}: 36 plies for stringer web and (45/0/-45/90/45/0/0/-45/0/0/-45/0/0/45/90/-45/0/45/45/0/-45/-45/0/45): 24 plies for stringer attachment flange. They are identical regardless of stiffener numbers.

All panels were subjected to drop weight impact tests at the one leg center of an attachment flange with normalized energy level of 4 J/mm and 6.7 J/mm. All impacts were given to the specimens at room temperature by using an instrumented drop weight machine. Delaminated area in projection was measured by the same ultrasonic C-scanner as in the previous section and it was found that delamination areas are quite small for 4J/mm panels due to high fracture toughness of CF/PIXA. Relationships between delamination area and normalized impact energy are shown in Fig.4 for all specimens of 4 and 6.7 J/mm with comparison of the authors' previous data for CF/PEEK stiffened panels including hat shaped stiffener ones¹⁰. This figure indicates that CF/PIXA has more excellent impact resistance at least at room temperature than CF/PEEK. This property can be ascribed rather to the used fusion bonding film

One practically difficult point in high temperature CAI tests of stiffened structures is how to clamp loading edges. Although we can rely on a potting agent which is a mixture of epoxy resin and some filler at room temperature tests, it is very hard to find a high-temperature potting agent. Instead of potting technique, clamping fixtures of stainless steel were developed for both types of panels and a photograph of one set for 2T panels is shown in Fig.5.

Fig.4 Relationships between Normalized Impact Energy and Projected Delamination Area

Fig.5 Photo of Loading End Fixture

By tightening many screws, clamped boundary conditions at the loading ends were approximately realized, although one concern is a mismatch in coefficients of thermal expansion between CF/PIXA and steel. The present experience by the authors implies that this concern is not so serious at least within 180 deg. C.

OUTLINE OF COMPRESSION TESTS AFTER IMPACT

Compression tests at room temperature and 180 deg. C were conducted for 1T-01,03,04, 2T-01,05 panels, and 1T-02,05, 2T-02,03,04 panels, respectively. In room temperature tests, data acquisition devices were normal strain gages, dial gages for out-of-plane deflections, an acoustic emission sensor network system for AE location identification and a Moire-topography camera for obtaining out-of-plane deflection contour. Numbers of gages are 14 for 1T-01 and 30 for 2T-01 (in channels). In elevated temperature tests, the same high temperature grade gages as flat plate cases were used with a polyimide strain gage cement (PI-32). The gages were only data acquisition pick-ups except for AE trials at high temperature. Gage quantities were 14 for 1T-01 and 24 for 2T-02.

Fig. 6 Photograph of High Temperature CAI Test for 2T Panel

Typical gage maps are already shown in Figs. 2 and 3 where some gages were glued in back to back locations. Gage #3 was placed on an impact indentation. Used data logger was an HP 3852A system. Acoustic emission sensors (PAC-R15) for universal purpose were tried in high temperature tests and it was verified that they worked at least in 180 deg. C atmosphere.

Loading edge conditions were close to clamped owing to the stainless end platens described above. Stainless steel tubes with sharpened slits acting as knife edges were installed along both side edges so that simply supported conditions were approximately realized. Compression load was applied by the Instron 1128 screw driven machine directly through an upper end platen. A photograph of an elevated temperature test of a 2T stiffened panel (02) is shown in Fig.6. Because of a shortage of width in the environmental chamber, it can be seen that the panel was placed diagonally to it. Also, acoustic emission sensors can be identified by lead wires. Due to such an in-chamber test piece arrangement, Moire-topography pictures could never be taken at all elevated temperature tests.

DISCUSSIONS ABOUT CAI TEST RESULTS

Stress-strain behavior of 2T-01 panel tested at room temperature and 2T-04 panel tested at 180 deg. C is indicated in Figs. 7 and 8, respectively. It can be clearly seen that local buckling in a stiffener bay occurred at 257MPa in 2T-01 and that considerable increase in stress was observed before the final failure. Buckling mode taken by the Moire camera for a different RT panel (2T-05) just before failure is shown in Fig. 9 where buckling stress is 228MPa. Four half waves of the out-of-plane deflection along the loading direction can be observed in the picture if examined carefully (the lowest one is difficult to be identified). High temperature stress-strain behavior of 2T-04 shown in Fig. 8 also describes a considerable postbuckling behavior. In the reported¹¹⁾ high temperature test (2T-02), a sudden failure after buckling was observed. According to an ultrasonic inspection of this panel, several indications of intermediate level were suspected to be the cause of this sort of premature failure behavior. No ultrasonic indications corresponding to fabrication defects were found for new panels (03-05). A very remarkable property of CF/PIXA panels bonded by PIXA-M film that delamination is not a trigger of the final failure will be discussed later.

This reverse relation can be regarded as a proof of excellent damage tolerance of these CF/PIXA stiffened panels. They exhibited much better CAI strengths than CF/ PEEK panels.

Relationships between temperature and CAI strengths for heat-resistant polymer composites are shown in Fig.11 with the same legends for the present stiffened panels as Fig.10. Other legend data, CF/PIXA: SACMA, CF/PI-SP: NASA, and CF/BMI are results of flat plate CAI strengths and identical to those appeared already in Fig.1.

Fig. 10 Relationships between Normalized Impact Energy and Stiffened Panel CAI Strengths

This figure implies that panel CAI strengths of CF/PIXA are compatible with flat plate behavior. It is also suggested that some panels of insufficient quality exhibited lower CAI strength. A finding that enough post-buckling behavior can be observed even at high temperature of 180 deg. C for polymer composites if the fabrication process is appropriate is quite favorable for future HSCT structural design. By summarizing the results in Figs. 10 and 11, and Fig.1, it can be stated that damage tolerance capability of CF/PIXA structure is excellent even at elevated temperatures.

This finding suggests that a great potential of CF/PIXA system has been demonstrated as a candidate for HSCT composite structures. It should be also noted that these CAI results provide the basis of an adjustment of actual allowable stress or strain in a CF/PIXA model wing box test under simulated variable environments which continues now.

Fig. 11 Relationships between Temperature and CAI Strengths for Heat-Resistant Polymer Composites

COMPARISON OF FEA BUCKLING RESULTS WITH EXPERIMENTS

Numerical calculations using finite element analysis (FEA) were conducted to predict buckling stress and modes at room and elevated temperatures. Software package of NISA-II was used in the analysis. Quadrilateral laminate shell element of 8 node was selected as the base element. Loading and side edges were assumed as fixed and simply supported, respectively.

Metallic end fixture was not incorporated into the model. Used material properties at room temperature and 180 deg. C are given in Table 2.

Table 2 Input Material Properties for CF/PIXA UD Lamina for FEA

Temperature	RT	100	180	230 deg.C
E_L (GPa)	152.4	152.4	152.4	152.4
E_T (GPa)	8.06	7.65	6.87	5.66
G_{LT} (GPa)	4.69	4.40	3.70	2.80
ν_{LT}	0.344	0.344	0.344	0.344
ν_{TT}	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5

Calculated buckling mode at RT is given in Fig.12. If we compare the experimental mode in Fig.9 and this numerical mode, extreme similarity can be found including slight skewness in the shape and small deflection in the lowest contour. Skewness is presumably brought by local asymmetry in stacking sequence in skin-attachment flange.

Fig. 12 Calculated Buckling Mode at RT

Relationships between initial buckling stress and temperature are plotted in Fig13 where two cases of loading edge boundary conditions are adopted, clamped and simply supported. Because skin thickness was assumed to be 2.664mm for 2T-01 with 257Mpa buckling stress, clamped result shows a good agreement at this point, whereas a slight discrepancy can be found for 2T-05 panel with 2.574mm skin and 228Mpa buckling stress. It can be expected that better predictions will be obtained if we assume the corresponding thickness for each panel. Of course, the clamped boundary condition will provide better predictions. In general, buckling predictions in mode and stress coincide extremely well with experimental results. If we compare Fig.11 and 13 in detail with considering vertical axis difference, it can be observed that compression strength reduction in CF/PIXA stiffened panels at high temperature is not fully caused by buckling stress reduction but also by deterioration in postbuckling behavior. Nonlinear portion of the analysis treating postbuckling is currently undertaken and discussions will be presented in oral presentations.

Fig. 13 Relationships between Initial Buckling Stress and Temperature
($t_{\text{skin}}=2.664\text{mm}$)

CONCLUSIONS

CAI strengths of stiffened panels of CF/PIXA were obtained at room temperature and elevated temperature of 180 deg. C. The following findings are identified through the experimentation and corresponding numerical analysis particularly done for initial buckling prediction.

1. CF/PIXA stiffened panels demonstrate their excellent impact resistance at ambient temperature. It is even better than CF/PEEK and may be provided by Regulus PIXA-M fusion bonding film used between skin and attachment flange.
2. Special end clamping devices were developed and proven to be effective in high temperature CAI tests of stiffened panels.
3. Ordinary AE sensors work so far as tested temperature (180 deg. C).
4. Stiffened panel with two T stringers tested in room temperature exhibited substantial post-buckling behavior. The panel tested at high temperature also showed enough postbuckling behavior if fusion bonding is well accomplished.
5. Room temperature CAI values of one 1T panel indicated some strength deterioration due to a defect between skin and stringer.
6. Summary of all structural CAI data of various materials provides that damage tolerance properties of CF/PIXA is remarkably excellent even at elevated temperature if structure is well fabricated.
7. Delaminated regions by impact were not triggers of the final failure in the present stiffened panel tests owing to excellent delamination evolution resistance of the present fusion bonding.
8. CAI results of stiffened panels are in good consistency with flat plate CAI results of the same material done in SACMA method.
9. Obtained results are directly used for a determination of allowable strain or stress in a model wing box test of CF/PIXA under variable environments.

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